

Burnout and Self-Efficacy Towards Job Satisfaction of IT Sector Employees: The Mediating Role of Work Engagement

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: This study purposes at testing the structures of three variables such as burnout, self-efficacy, towards job satisfaction among employees in the Information technology sector in Bangalore City. The study also pursues to discover the probable correlations between these latent variables.

Methods: The quantitative method approach was used with a snowball sampling technique. The sample of the study is 386 in Bangalore City. To collect the data, a structured measurement scale was used for the survey purpose. Hypotheses were framed based on the conceptual framework of the study. The constructed hypotheses were tested by using statistical tools such as regression analysis to validate the purpose.

Findings: The findings of the study exposes that there is a significant relationship between burnout and self-efficacy toward job satisfaction. Stress burnout is essential for a recent employee in a competitive environment.

Conclusion: Significant burnout - self-efficacy relationships were observed in the Indian context, although the strength of relationship across burnout and self-efficacy component. There is insufficient research on emotional intelligence and turnover intention with moderating effect on job satisfaction.

Keywords: Burnout, Self-efficacy, Job Satisfaction, Employee engagement, Information Technology Employees

1. INTRODUCTION

Burnout creates because of persistent pressure in the workplace when work necessities and laborers' apparent capacities don't coordinate (Brown, 2012; Maslach *et al.*, 2001). Burnout is viewed as normal in various human administration occupations and it is much of the time utilized as a sign of unfortunate prosperity or a nearby connection between representatives' psychological and actual wellbeing (Maslach *et al.*, 2001). Late meta-examinations showed that burnout was related to business-related factors, for example, work hours or work setting (Limet *et al.*, 2010), and social help from collaborators (Kay-Eccles, 2012). Past the ecological supporters of burnout, individual and self-

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administrative elements that act as significant assets in working with adapting are additionally critical to consider. These self-administrative factors incorporate locus of control, good faith, and self-adequacy (Alarconet *al.*, 2009). Though burnout addresses a critical and one of the most often concentrated results of occupation stress (Maslach et al., 2001), self-viability convictions address key modifiable insights that might shield laborers from adverse results of occupation stress (Brown, 2012). This study gives a union of proof to the connections between burnout and self-viability insights.

In the improvement of the idea of self viability, more exploration worries about the capacity of this idea for a person's mental discernments and ways of behaving. Self adequacy is demonstrated to affect how individuals think, feel, and act. People with low self viability have low confidence and are skeptical about their achievements. Low self viability is related to sensations of sorrow, uneasiness, and powerlessness (Bandura, 1997). Corresponding to managing change, low confidence and negativity, as well as instability, have been proposed to affect mental pressure (Bandura, 1997). Accordingly, it is proposed that self viability is connected with mental work pressure. Blechazet *al.*, (2004) distinguish self-viability as a significant variable for the outcome of progress. To ease the job pressure and occupation burnout of CPMs and further develop their work execution, most analysts centeraround the impact of hierarchical help or social help. Nonetheless, just depending on authoritative help or responsibility isn't adequate to direct job pressure and occupation burnout.

Research Objectives:

1. to explore the association between burnout and self-efficacy
2. to identify the influencing factors of job satisfaction
3. to know the mediating effect of work engagement between burnout, self-efficacy, and job satisfaction

2. LITERARY REVISED

2.1 Burnout

The term burnout first showed up during the 1970s, particularly among individuals in human administration. The underlying examination was described by different exploratory investigations which had the objective of articulating the peculiarity (Brown, 2012). In the beginning stages, there was no normal settlement on the meaning of burnout and specialists involved various strategies in the methodology of examining the idea. Notwithstanding these distinctions, there was a typical agreement around three center aspects that were expected to comprise the idea: profound weariness, depersonalization, and decreased individual achievement. Various methodologies inside the field of burnout research exist (Friedman 2003; Maslach *et al.*, 2001). The most articulated work is presumably directed by Maslach who fostered a multi-faceted hypothesis of burnout (Maslach *et al.*, 2001). This hypothetical direction thinks about the three aspects and is by all accounts the most predominant methodology in the field (Schaufeli *et al.*, 2009). The characterizes burnout as a mental disorder that includes a drawn-out reaction to stressors in the working environment (Prati *et al.*, 2010). The experience of burnout is conceptualized as coming about because of long-haul word-related pressure, particularly among laborers who manage others within some limit.

2.2 Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy is a critical component in Bandura's social mental hypothesis (Bandura 1997). The social mental hypothesis accentuates the involvement and exercise of human organization - a thought that individuals can practice some impact over what they do. Individuals are seen as self-sorting out, proactive, self-intelligent, self-managed, and taking part in their turn of events (Salanova *et al.*, 2002). Individuals can influence their own decisions and have the right stuff to control their thinking examples and feelings. Their thought process, acceptance, and feeling make rules for conduct (Tsouloupas *et al.*, 2010). The view of the real world, and hence conduct, is impacted by the control and impact they experience over their lives (Unsworth & Mason, 2012). Human working is seen as the result of a unique transaction of individual, conduct, and natural impacts. This is the underpinning of proportional determinism which proposes that individual elements, conduct, and ecological impacts make connections that outcome in a triadic correspondence (Federici & Skaalvik, 2011). Self-efficacy is the singular's conviction about what the person can accomplish in a given setting (Chen & Scannapieco, 2010). These convictions impact the decisions of activity, how much exertion is consumed on a movement, and how lengthy individuals will drive forward while confronting obstacles. Self-efficacy likewise has an element that impressively affects understudy accomplishment (Hattie, 2003). Has incorporated a few examinations connected with instructors' Self-efficacy, reasoning that this disorder significantly affects understudy learning. Different specialists (Taylor, 2010) have prescribed working on educators' Self-efficacy to further develop understudy accomplishment.

2.3 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction was defined in different ways according to the social contexts, which agrees with the fact that it is a multidimensional concept. As stated by Locke (1976), job satisfaction is an emotional situation as a consequence of people's job experience. Moreover, De Simone & Planta (2017) indicated job satisfaction as an emotional and perceptual response to the specific characteristic of a job. Further, Bargsted (2019) argued that job satisfaction is a pleasant feeling that comes from the insight that people's job satisfies or allows for the satisfaction of one's outstanding values came from their work. Later, Byrne, (2010) pointed out, that satisfaction and commitment are necessary factors to improve the teaching and learning process. Castillo and Cano (2004) categorized job satisfaction into two types: general satisfaction and specific satisfaction. General satisfaction is the overall and comprehensive satisfaction that is defined as an overall assessment of a people's perception of their work. Specific satisfaction has been defined as an assessment of different aspects of the work. Some of the examples related to these aspects consist of monetary benefits, working conditions, relationships with colleagues and superiors, and the nature of the work itself.

2.4 Employee Engagement

Work engagement is a factor related to job performance. Likewise, workers with high job commitment may be willing to take on additional job roles, which reflect on job self-efficacy and performance in task accomplishment, creativity, and quality (Dai *et al.*, 2018). Engaged employees have an energetically effective connection to the work context. Therefore, they consider their work challenging rather than stressful and demanding. This, on the one hand, leads to increased levels of job performance (Calizaya *et al.*, 2019), and on the other hand, it could favor buffering benefits against the negative effects of stressors and job burnout.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data and Samples

The researcher has chosen the employees who are working in the information technology field in Bangalore city as considered the population of the study. The sample size is 386 which is drawn by using the snowball sampling method. The data was collected from the respondents through google forms. With the support of a measurement scale, the data was collected.

3.2 Methods and Measure

In the survey, there is 5-point Likert scale was used to know the preference level of the respondents. The measurement scale consists of five sections. The first part deals with the demographic profile of the respondents, the second part contains deals with burnout, it has 5-items adopted from Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI). The third part about self-efficacy from Professional Efficacy Questionnaire was used. The fourth consists of job satisfaction and has 18-items adopted from the Job Satisfaction Survey and Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire. Finally, the fifth part deals with work engagement and has 9-items adapted from Utrecht Work Engagement, and the researcher valid responses were scrutinized without any outliers.

3.3 Conceptual Framework Model

Figure 1: The conceptual framework model

3.4 Hypotheses Development

H₁: Burnout is positively and significantly related to Work Engagement

H₂: Self-efficacy is positively and significantly related to Work Engagement

H₃: Work Engagement is positively and significantly related to Job satisfaction

H₄: Work Engagement mediates the relationship between Burnout and Turnover Intention toward Job satisfaction

4. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Out of 386 respondents, 56 respondents belonged Below 25 years old, 105 respondents belonged to 26 - 35 years old, 180 respondents belonged to 36 - 45 years old, and 45 respondents belonged to 46 and above years old. In the gender category, 178 were male and 208 were female. Based on monthly income, 78 respondents have less than Rs.25000, 99 respondents have Rs.25001 - Rs.50000, 138 respondents have Rs.50001 - Rs.75000, and 71 respondents have Rs.75001 and above. Under the experience category, 66 respondents had Below 1 year of experience, 123 respondents had 2 - 3 years of experience, 118 respondents had 4 - 5 years of experience, and 79 respondents had 6 and above years of experience.

Table 1: The reliability and validity of the constructs

Variables	Job Satisfaction	Alpha	AVE	Burnout	Self-Efficacy	Work Engagement
Burnout	0.968	0.917	0.882	0.939		
Self-efficacy	0.954	0.862	0.786	0.714	0.924	
Work engagement	0.971	0.943	0.854	0.707	0.756	0.850

The reliability and validity of the constructs were measured. The Cronbach's alpha for burnout is 0.917; self-efficacy has 0.862, and work engagement has 0.943 which is greater than the standard level of 0.7.

Table 2: Results of Regression

Variable	Job Satisfaction		
	Beta	t	p
Burnout	.058	1.865	.653
Self-Efficacy	.071	2.370	.027
Work Engagement	.651	8.672	.018
F	70.629		.000
R-Square	.289		
Adjusted R Square	.231		

In this study, the influence of stress burnout and self-efficacy on job satisfaction with the mediating effect of work engagement was analyzed by regression analysis. According to the findings stress burnout and self-efficacy on job satisfaction among the employee in Information technology has a significant relationship. However, stress burnout has no significant impact on individual job satisfaction. On the contrary, some studies recommend several results. The research is exposed that stress burnout has no relationship with job satisfaction and self-efficacy has a positive relationship with job satisfaction. Work engagement mediated the relationship between burnout and self-efficacy with job satisfaction of the employees in the information technology field.

Table 3: Results of Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses	Results
H ₁ : Burnout is positively and significantly related to Work Engagement	Not Supported
H ₂ : Self-efficacy is positively and significantly related to Work Engagement	Supported
H ₃ : Work Engagement is positively and significantly related to Job satisfaction	Supported
H ₄ : Work Engagement mediates the relationship between Burnout and Turnover Intention toward Job satisfaction	Supported

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Empirical Model

(Note: ** represents Significant at the .01 level, * represents Significant at the .05 level, and n.s denotes non-significance)

5. CONCLUSION

The present study proposed to investigate two main aspects influencing the job satisfaction of the employees in the information technology sector. From the results, the researcher concluded that self-efficacy has a significant positive effect on employee job satisfaction and stress burnout has a negative impact on job satisfaction. More precisely, it aimed to explore the interaction and relationship between these aspects, namely stress burnout and self-efficacy on job satisfaction with the mediating impact of work engagement. The regression output specifies that the positive associations between self-efficacy and negative associations of burnout occurred among individual employees or those with more work experience. The results provide perceptions into the interpretation of these relations. Older workers have a better-recognized relation between the protecting principles about their capacity to deal with stressful occasions and inferior burnout. They may be further likely to practice this protective resource successfully, to lesser their burnout. From an organizational perception, a few fascinating practical inferences can be made. Human resource managers can use it to develop strategies to reduce job stress in the organizational climate. Because self-efficacy of change is of significance to job stress, when choosing new workers during the exchange period, human resource managers may require to estimate the self-efficacy of the candidates. Employees must be given chances to contribute to the training on which way to escalate their self-efficacy and with that, reduce stress.

REFERENCES

1. Brown, C. G. (2012). A systematic review of the relationship between self-efficacy and burnout in teachers. *Educational & Child Psychology*, 29, 47-63
2. Maslach, C., Schaufeli, W. B., & Leiter, M. P. (2001). Job burnout. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52, 397-422. doi:10.1146/annurev.psych.52.1.397
3. Lim, N., Kim, E. K., Kim, H., Yang, E., & Lee, S. (2010). Individual and work-related factors influencing burnout of mental health professionals: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Employment Counseling*, 47, 86-96. doi:10.1002/j.2161-1920.2010.tb00093.x
4. Alarcon, G., Eschleman, K. J., & Bowling, N. A. (2009). Relationship between personality variables and burnout: A metaanalysis. *Work & Stress*, 23, 244-263. doi:10.1080/02678370903282600
5. Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. New York, NY: Freeman
6. Blecharz, J., Luszczynska, A., Scholz, U., Schwarzer, R., Siekanska, M., & Cieslak, R. (2014). Predicting performance and performance satisfaction: The role of mindfulness and beliefs about the ability to deal with social barriers in sport. *Anxiety, Stress, & Coping*, 27, 270-287. doi:10.1080/10615806.2013.839989
7. Brown, C. G. (2012). A systematic review of the relationship between self-efficacy and burnout in teachers. *Educational & Child Psychology*, 29, 47-63.

8. Friedman, I. A. (2003). Self-efficacy and burnout in teaching: The importance of interpersonal-relations efficacy. *Social Psychology of Education*, 6, 191–215. doi:10.1023/A:1024723124467
9. Schaufeli, W. B., Leiter, M., & Maslach, C. (2009). Burnout: 35 years of research and practice. *Career Development International*, 14, 204–220. doi:10.1108/13620430910966406
10. Prati, G., Pietrantonio, L., & Cicognani, E. (2010). Self-efficacy moderates the relationship between stress appraisal and quality of life among rescue workers. *Anxiety, Stress, & Coping*, 23, 463–470. doi:10.1080/10615800903431699
11. Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. New York, NY: Freeman.
12. Salanova, M., Peiró, J. M., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2002). Self-efficacy specificity and burnout among information technology workers: An extension of the job demand-control model. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 11, 1–25. doi:10.1080/13594320143000735
13. Tsouloupas, C. N., Carson, R. L., Matthews, R., Grawitch, M. J., & Barber, L. K. (2010). Exploring the association between teachers' perceived student misbehaviour and emotional exhaustion: The importance of teacher efficacy beliefs and emotion regulation. *Educational Psychology*, 30, 173–189. doi:10.1080/01443410903494460
14. Unsworth, K. L., & Mason, C. M. (2012). Help yourself: The mechanisms through which a self-leadership intervention influences strain. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 17, 235–245. doi:10.1037/a0026857
15. Federici, R. A., & Skaalvik, E. M. (2011). Principal self-efficacy and work engagement: Assessing a Norwegian principal self-efficacy scale. *Social Psychology of Education*. doi:10.1007/s11218-011-9160-4.
16. Chen, S. Y., & Scannapieco, M. (2010). The influence of job satisfaction on child welfare worker's desire to stay: An examination of the interaction effect of self-efficacy and supportive supervision. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 32(4), 482–486
17. Hattie, J. (2003). Teachers make a difference: What is the research evidence?. In Paper presented at the building teacher quality: What does the research tell us ACER research conference. Australian Council for Educational Research (ACER) Teachers Make a Difference, What Is the Research Evidence? Distinguishing Expert Teachers from Novice and Experienced Teachers http://research.acer.edu.au/research_conference_2003%0Ahttp://research.acer.edu.au/research_conference_2003.
18. Taylor, R. (2010). Leadership to improve student achievement: Focus the culture on learning. *AASA Journal of Scholarship and Practice*, 7(1), 10–23.
19. Locke, E. A. (1976). The nature and causes of job satisfaction. In M. D. Dunnette (Ed.), *Handbook of industrial and organizational psychology*, 1, 297–1,349
20. Bargsted M, Ramirez-Vielma R, Yeves J. (2019) Professional self-efficacy and job satisfaction: the mediator role of work design. *J Work Organ Psychol*. 35, 157-163.
21. Byrne, B. M. (2010). *Structural equation modeling with AMOS: Basic concepts, applications, and programming*. New York: Routledge
22. Dai YD, Zhuang WL, Lu SC, Huan TC. (2018) Work engagement or job burnout? Psychological ownership amongst the employees of international tourist hotels. *Tour Rev*. 76, 1243-1259.
23. Calizaya Lopez JM, Morales Palao B, Pinto Pomareda HL, Bellido Medina RS. (2019) Analisis del compromiso laboral en colaboradores de gobiernos locales de la ciudad de Arequipa, Peru. *Univ Cienc y Tecnol*. 24, 13-19.